

Latest NOvA Oscillation Results from 10 Years of Data

Maria Flavia Cicala, for the NOvA Collaboration

[arXiv:2509.04361](https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.04361)

NuPhys 2026, King's College London

7 January 2026

Neutrino oscillation and the PMNS matrix

Neutrino (ν) properties inform the evolution of the universe

ν are extremely difficult to detect

- Neutral charge
- Tiny mass
- Weak force interaction only

ν can oscillate between three flavours: ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ via the PMNS matrix

Neutrino oscillation and the PMNS matrix

Neutrino (ν) properties inform the evolution of the universe

ν are extremely difficult to detect

- Neutral charge
- Tiny mass
- Weak force interaction only

Flavor	Mass
m_1 Neutrino1	
m_2 Neutrino2	
m_3 Neutrino3	

ν can oscillate between three flavours: ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ via the PMNS matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{CP}} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Neutrino oscillation and the PMNS matrix

Neutrino (ν) properties inform the evolution of the universe

ν are extremely difficult to detect

- Neutral charge
- Tiny mass
- Weak force interaction only

Flavor	Mass
m_1 Neutrino1	
m_2 Neutrino2	
m_3 Neutrino3	

ν can oscillate between three flavours: ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ via the PMNS matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{CP}} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

3 rotation angles: $\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}$ + 1 complex phase: δ

Oscillation probability also depends on $\Delta m_{ij}^2 = m_i^2 - m_j^2$ and $\frac{L}{E}$

Neutrino oscillation and the PMNS matrix

Neutrino (ν) properties inform the evolution of the universe

ν are extremely difficult to detect

- Neutral charge
- Tiny mass
- Weak force interaction only

Flavor	Mass
m_1 Neutrino1	
m_2 Neutrino2	
m_3 Neutrino3	

ν can oscillate between three flavours: ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ via the PMNS matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{CP}} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Neutrino oscillation experiments aim to **measure PMNS parameters**

Why study 3-flavour neutrino oscillations?

3 flavour oscillation measurements is the primary goal:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Why study 3-flavour neutrino oscillations?

3 flavour oscillation measurements is the primary goal:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Neutrino mass ordering

normal hierarchy (NH)

inverted hierarchy (IH)

Why study 3-flavour neutrino oscillations?

3 flavour oscillation measurements is the primary goal:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Neutrino mass ordering

normal hierarchy (NH)

inverted hierarchy (IH)

Symmetry

between μ and τ flavours?

Measure θ_{23} !

Why study 3-flavour neutrino oscillations?

3 flavour oscillation measurements is the primary goal:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Neutrino mass ordering

normal hierarchy (NH)

inverted hierarchy (IH)

Symmetry

between μ and τ flavours?

Measure θ_{23} !

CP symmetry violation?

Measure δ_{CP} !

The NOvA Experiment

Long baseline neutrino oscillation experiment

- NuMI neutrino beam at FNAL
- Near Detector measures neutrinos before oscillations
- Far Detector measurements after oscillation

The NOvA Experiment

Long baseline neutrino oscillation experiment

- NuMI neutrino beam at FNAL
- Near Detector measures neutrinos before oscillations
- Far Detector measurements after oscillation

3 flavour oscillation measurements is the primary goal:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Broader goals:

- Sterile neutrino search
- Neutrino cross section measurements
- Supernova neutrinos
- Cosmic ray particles

The NuMI beam

The NOvA detectors

ND and FD are functionally identical

The NOvA detectors

ND and FD are functionally identical

Extruded PVC cells filled with 1.1 million litres of liquid scintillator

Cells arranged in alternating directions for 3D reconstruction

The NOvA detectors

ND and FD are functionally identical

Extruded PVC cells filled with 1.1 million litres of liquid scintillator

Charged particle

Charged particles resulting from ν interactions interact with the scintillator producing light
 Light is detected by 32-pixel Avalanche PhotoDiodes (APDs)

3-Flavour neutrino oscillation analysis

Aim:

observe **flavour change** between ND and FD

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Caveats:

uncertainties on neutrino flux,
cross section,
detector response

3-Flavour neutrino oscillation analysis

Aim:

observe **flavour change** between ND and FD

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Caveats:

uncertainties on neutrino flux,
cross section,
detector response

1. Select ν_μ and ν_e at ND and FD

3-Flavour neutrino oscillation analysis

Aim:

observe **flavour change** between ND and FD

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Caveats:

uncertainties on neutrino flux,
cross section,
detector response

1. Select ν_μ and ν_e at ND and FD

3-Flavour neutrino oscillation analysis

Aim:

observe **flavour change** between ND and FD

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Caveats:

uncertainties on neutrino flux,
cross section,
detector response

1. Select ν_μ and ν_e at ND and FD

2. Fit FD neutrino energy data

3-Flavour neutrino oscillation analysis

Aim:

observe **flavour change** between ND and FD

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$)
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ ($\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$)

Caveats:

uncertainties on neutrino flux,
cross section,
detector response

1. Select ν_μ and ν_e at ND and FD

2. Fit FD nei

Joint simultaneous fit to $\nu_\mu, \nu_e, \bar{\nu}_\mu, \bar{\nu}_e$

Selection Criteria

Event topologies

Selection Criteria

Event topologies

ν_μ selection

ν_e selection

Oscillation Fit

Aim: extract $\Delta m_{32}^2, \sin^2 \theta_{23}, \delta_{CP}$

Constrain all other PMNS parameters except θ_{13} by PDG values

Oscillation Fit

Aim: extract $\Delta m_{32}^2, \sin^2\theta_{23}, \delta_{CP}$

Constrain all other PMNS parameters except θ_{13} by PDG values

Option 1:

θ_{13} unconstrained, NOvA only

Option 2:

θ_{13} constrained by Daya Bay 1D value
 $\sin^2 2\theta_{13} = 0.0851 \pm 0.0024$

Option 3:

$\Delta m_{32}^2, \theta_{13}$ constrained by Daya Bay 2D interval
 (PRL 130, 161802)

Oscillation Fit

Aim: extract $\Delta m_{32}^2, \sin^2 \theta_{23}, \delta_{CP}$

Constrain all other PMNS parameters except θ_{13} by PDG values

Poisson log-likelihood ratio

About 60 nuisance parameters to handle our systematic uncertainties

Use a Bayesian approach with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo to sample the posterior probability distribution and build credible intervals

Oscillation Fit

Aim: extract $\Delta m_{32}^2, \sin^2 \theta_{23}, \delta_{CP}$

Constrain all other PMNS parameters except θ_{13} by PDG values

Poisson log-likelihood ratio

About 60 nuisance parameters to handle our systematic uncertainties

Use a Bayesian approach with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo to sample the posterior probability distribution and build credible intervals

Outcome: hierarchy, octant, CP violation

Results!

Results: ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ Data at FD

384 events, 11.3 background

106 events, 1.7 background

Results: ν_e and $\bar{\nu}_e$ Data at FD

Total Observed	181	Range
Total Prediction	186.2	119-250
Wrong-sign	1.8	0.6-1.7
Beam Bkgd.	53.7	
Cosmic Bkgd.	6.2	
Total Bkgd.	61.7	61-63

Total Observed	32	Range
Total Prediction	30.4	28-38
Wrong-sign	2.1	1.0-3.2
Beam Bkgd.	9.0	
Cosmic Bkgd.	1.1	
Total Bkgd.	12.2	11-13

Results in $\nu_2 - \nu_3$ mixing

Results in $\nu_2 - \nu_3$ mixing

Maximum mixing allowed in both cases at less than 1 σ

Reactor constraint results Upper Octant preference (2.2 Bayes factor, 69% probability)

Results in $\nu_2 - \nu_3$ mixing

Normal mass ordering

v11 2024.10: git.jinr.ru/nu/osc

* 2024 result, PRELIMINARY

Preliminary
Published

§ based on 2020 ana.

† Neutrino-2022 result

¶ SKI-V result, arXiv:2311.05105

‡ based on SK IV and T2K 2020, arXiv:2405.12488

Results: δ_{CP} and mass ordering

No strong asymmetry in rates of appearance of ν_e and $\bar{\nu}_e$

Normal Ordering favours CP conservation

Inverted Ordering excludes non-CP violation ($\delta_{CP} = \frac{\pi}{2}$) at $> 3\sigma$

Results: δ_{CP} and mass ordering

No strong asymmetry in rates of appearance of ν_e and $\bar{\nu}_e$
 Normal Ordering favours CP conservation
 Inverted Ordering excludes non-CP violation ($\delta_{CP} = \frac{\pi}{2}$) at $> 3\sigma$

Normal Ordering preference with Bayes Factor 3.2, 76% posterior probability ($\sim 1.4\sigma$)

Results: δ_{CP} and mass ordering

θ_{13} unconstrained
(NOvA only)
BF: 2.2, 69% posterior

Daya Bay 1D θ_{13}
constraint
BF: 3.2, 76% posterior (1.4σ)

Daya Bay 2D ($\Delta m_{32}^2, \theta_{13}$)
constraint
BF: 3.2, 76% posterior (1.4σ)

Reactor constraints strengthen the preference for NO

Summary

First 3- flavour oscillation study from NOvA since 2020:

- 10 years of data, doubling the neutrino-mode dataset.
- Updated simulation: improved light response model and neutron propagation uncertainty.

Results:

- The most precise single experiment measurement of Δm_{32}^2 (1.5%).
- Data favours a region where matter and CP violation effects are degenerate.

Strong synergy with reactor measurements:

- Constraint on θ_{13} enhances upper octant preference (69% odds).
- Constraint on Δm_{32}^2 enhances normal ordering preference (87% odds).

More data to come in 2026!

Backup

Oscillation Probability

$$|\nu_\alpha\rangle = \sum_i U_{\alpha i}^* |\nu_i\rangle$$

Mixing matrix

$$P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = \left| \sum_i U_{\alpha i}^* e^{-i \frac{m_i^2 L}{2E}} U_{\beta i} \right|^2$$

- The oscillation probabilities depend on:
 - Neutrino energy (E_ν)
 - Distance between the source and the detector (“baseline” L)
 - Squared mass differences ($\Delta m_{21}^2, \Delta m_{32}^2$)
 - Parameters of the mixing matrix: 3 angles and 1 phase ($\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}, \delta_{CP}$)

Oscillation Probability

Muon (anti) neutrino disappearance probability

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu) \approx 1 - \left(\sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\theta_{23}) + \cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{23}) \right) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta m^2 L}{4E}\right)$$

Electron (anti) neutrino appearance probability

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) \approx \left| \sqrt{P_{\text{atm}}} e^{-e(\Delta_{32} + \delta_{CP})} + \sqrt{P_{\text{sol}}} \right|^2$$

$$\approx P_{\text{atm}} + P_{\text{sol}} + 2\sqrt{P_{\text{atm}}P_{\text{sol}}} (\cos \Delta_{32} \cos \delta_{CP} \mp \sin \Delta_{32} \sin \delta_{CP})$$

$$\sqrt{P_{\text{atm}}} = \sin(\theta_{23}) \sin(2\theta_{13}) \frac{\sin(\Delta_{31} - aL)}{\Delta_{31} - aL} \Delta_{31}$$

$$\sqrt{P_{\text{sol}}} = \cos \theta_{23} \sin(2\theta_{12}) \frac{\sin(aL)}{aL} \Delta_{21}$$

$$\Delta_{jk} \equiv \frac{\Delta m_{jk}^2 L}{4E} \quad a = \frac{G_F N_e}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Oscillation channels

Flavor information comes from the associated charged lepton. CC channels available:

- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$
- $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\tau$
- $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu$
- $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$
- $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\tau$
- $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$
- $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$
- $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\tau$
- $\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\mu$
- $\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$
- $\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\tau$

No charged lepton: can't discriminate flavors. NC channels available:

- $\nu \rightarrow \nu$ NC
- $\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \bar{\nu}$ NC
- NC Total

PMNS matrix

- The mixing matrix can be written in terms of 3 angles and 1 phase. Usually factorized into components directly related to the experiments:

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} \square & \square & \square \\ \square & \square & \square \\ \square & \square & \square \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{+i\delta} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}, s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$

The (23) sector:
Atmospheric
and accelerator

The (13) sector:
Reactor and
accelerator

The (12) sector:
Solar and
reactor

- Current experiments \rightarrow precision measurements of the angles
- Poorly known: θ_{23} ($\sim 5\%$), δ_{CP} (\sim unconstrained)
 - Q: is θ_{23} maximal? i.e. is there symmetry in ν_{μ}, ν_{τ} mixing to ν_2, ν_3 ? If not, what is the octant?
 - Q: is $\delta_{CP} \neq 0, \pi$? i.e. is CP violated in the neutrino sector?

Cosmic rays at FD

1.1 billion
cosmic rays/day

Selection Criteria

Convolutional Neural networks used:

- PID stage
- Cosmic rejection stage

Other classifiers such as Boosted Decision Trees also used

ν_μ selection

ν_e selection

ν_e candidate selection

NOvA Simulation

- For NOvA's energy range and baseline the effect of the mass ordering is largest at lower energies in the range.
- Challenging for NOvA - predicted number of events in this region is small.
- Pursuing these events with a new BDT classifier.

Detector response characterisation

Most recent improvements in detector modelling include

- New light production model in mineral oil in both ND and FD
- New studies of stopping proton and muon candidates in data
- New MENATE model to better simulate neutron energy

Systematic Uncertainty

Extrapolation

- Observe data-MC differences at the ND, use them to modify the FD MC.
- Significantly reduces the impact of uncertainties correlated between detectors.
 - Especially effective at rate effects like the flux (7% to 0.3%).

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

T2K

Japan

NOvA

USA

Super Kamiokande

Near Detector

J-PARC

Fermilab

Far Detector

T2K

Joint Analysis Results

Zoya Vallari, Caltech

Feb 16, 2024

NOvA

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Analysis Strategy

- The experiments have **different analysis approaches** driven by **contrasting detector designs**.

27

Joint Analysis Results

Zoya Vallari, Caltech

Feb 16, 2024

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Comparison with NOvA-only & T2K-only fits

- The joint-fit **splits the difference in the Normal Ordering** where the individual experiments preferred differing phase-spaces and provides **tighter constraint in the Inverted Ordering** where there was good agreement between NOvA-only and T2K-only fits.

60

Joint Analysis Results

Zoya Vallari, Caltech

Feb 16, 2024

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Comparison with NOvA-only & T2K-only fits

- The 1D posterior in Δm_{32}^2 highlights the switch in the mass ordering preference when NOvA and T2K are combined.
- The joint-fit enhances the precision of Δm_{32}^2 over individual experiments.

	NOvA only	T2K only	NOvA+T2K
Bayes factor	2.07 Normal/Inverted ~67% : ~33% posterior	4.24 Normal/Inverted ~81% : ~19% posterior	1.36 Inverted/Normal ~58% : ~42% posterior

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Global Comparisons - δ_{CP}

- The δ_{CP} measurements are consistent across all experiments and their combinations.
- The uncertainty on δ_{CP} remains large.

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Global Comparisons – θ_{13}

- Daya Bay leads the precision on the measurement of θ_{13} with 2.8% uncertainty.
- Overall, the long-baseline measurements are consistent with reactor experiments, with larger consistency in the normal ordering than the inverted ordering.

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

Global Comparisons - Δm_{32}^2

- This analysis has the **smallest uncertainty on $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$** as compared to other previous measurements.

NOvA T2K Joint Fit

NOvA+T2K+DayaBay

- Including the Δm_{32}^2 constraint from the Daya Bay*, reverse the mass ordering preference back to the Normal Ordering.
- Overall, this analysis does not show a significant preference for either mass ordering.

*Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 161802, 2023

	NOvA - T2K w/o reactor	NOvA - T2K - 1D Daya Bay	NOvA - T2K - 2D Daya Bay
Bayes factor	<p>2.47 Inverted/Normal ~71% : ~29% posterior</p>	<p>1.34 Inverted/Normal ~57% : ~43% posterior</p>	<p>1.44 Normal/Inverted ~59% : ~41% posterior</p>

